

Synthesis of 1-Arylpiperazine Amides of 2-[4-(Methoxyphenyl)-1*H*,5*H*-pyridin-2,6-dione-1-yl]acetic, -propionic Acids

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During last two decades *N*-(ω -aminoalkyl)imide (1) has emerged as a promising pharmacophore. Over last few years we have synthesised a series of *N*-[3-(4-aryl-1-piperazinyl)alkyl]imides (2)¹. These imides show CNS depressant and cardiovascular activities.

Parallel to the preparation of these glutarimides we attempted the preparation of the corresponding glutaconimides, the unsaturated analogs of the glutarimides. Preparation of these compounds was found to be difficult. Modification of the central alkylene bridge in 1 changes the activity of the pharmacophore to a great extent. 1-Piperazine amides are reported to show diverse biological activities². The compounds to which we were attracted were 1-aryl-(4-phthaloylglycyl)/*dl*- α -alanyl)piperazines which possess antiparkinsonic activity³. Hence, we attempted the synthesis of 1-arylpiperazine amides (14, 15) of ω -[4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1*H*,5*H*-pyridin-2,6-dion-1-yl]acetic, -propionic acids (7, 8).

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)pentendioic acid (3) was prepared by the known method⁴. Compound 3 was treated with Ac₂O to obtain the corresponding anhydride (4). Compound 4 when fused with glycine (5) gave 7. The acid chloride (9) of 7, could not be prepared by treating it with SOCl₂ or PCl₅. In every case, a mixture of irresolvable products with some tarry mass was obtained. The direct condensation of 7 with 1-arylpiperazines was also not possible; at a low temperature the reaction did not proceed and at higher temperature excessive decomposition took place. Compound 7 was esterified to 10 using EtOH. The condensation of 10 with 1-arylpiperazine also failed. On this background, we had to attempt a new route to the synthesis 14 and 15.

Compound 4 as well as *N*-substituted glutaconimides exhibit keto-enol tautomerism. Thus, 7 can

exist in tautomeric forms 7a and 7b. The enolic OH can cyclise with the COOH group. When 7 was refluxed with Ac₂O, azalactone (11) was formed. It was neutral and insoluble in NaHCO₃. It slowly dissolved in aqueous NaOH. On heating with aqueous NaOH it dissolved and the solution on acidification regenerated the parent acid (7). Ir spectrum of 11 showed lactone CO at a very high wavenumber (1855 cm⁻¹). The pyridone CO appeared at 1700 cm⁻¹. The high value of the lactone CO suggested the presence of high strain in the lactone ring; it also suggested that the ring can be opened by a nucleophile.

When 11 was heated with a series of 1-arylpiperazines in boiling acetone the lactone ring opened up to give a series of 4-aryl-1-piperazinylamides of 2-[4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1*H*,5*H*-pyridin-2,6-dione-1-yl]ethanoic acid (14).

Encouraged by this observation, we planned to prepare the next higher homolog (15) of 14. When 4 was heated with 3-aminopropanoic acid (6), 8 was obtained. When 8 was heated with Ac₂O it cyclised to azalactone (12). In the ir spectrum of 12, the lactone CO appeared at 1800 cm⁻¹ at considerably low wavenumber than that in 11, indicating less strain in the molecule. The pyridone CO appeared at 1670 cm⁻¹. When 12 was refluxed with 1-arylpiperazines (13) in boiling acetone a series of 4-aryl-1-piperazine amides of 3-[4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1*H*,5*H*-pyridine-2,6-dion-1-yl]propanoic acid (15) were obtained.

Experimental

The m.p.s. were taken in open capillaries on a Campbell melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on Varian T-60 (60 MHz), Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) and Varian XL-100 spectrometers using TMS as internal standard.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)pentendioic acid (3) was prepared from citric acid, anisole and concentrated H₂SO₄⁴. Compound 3 on treatment with Ac₂O gave the corresponding anhydride (4). 1-Arylpiperazines were prepared from anilines and diethanolamine following the reported procedure⁵.

2-[4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1*H*,5*H*-pyridin-2,6-dion-1-yl]ethanoic acid (7): A mixture of 4 (4.8 g, 20 mmol) and glycine (1.8 g, 24 mmol) was heated at

150–55° for 1 h. The resulting solid was dissolved in aqueous NaHCO₃ and the solution was treated with animal charcoal and acidified with concentrated HCl. The solid was crystallised from HOAc-H₂O (90 : 10, v/v), (4.18 g, 68%), m.p. 239–40° (Found : C, 61.10 ; H, 4.76 ; N, 5.08. C₁₄H₁₃NO₃ calcd. for : C, 61.10 ; H, 4.75 ; N, 5.10%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 790 and 1 750 (imide CO), 1 670 (COOH), 1 610 (C=C) and 1 250 cm⁻¹ (C—O).

7-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2,3-dihydro-5H(1,3)oxazolo-[3,2-a]pyridin-2,5-dione (11) : A mixture of 7 (8 g, 30 mmol) and Ac₂O (8 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The solution was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with water and then with acetone, (4.86 g, 63%), m.p. 229–30° (Found : C, 65.32 ; H, 4.32 ; N, 5.43. C₁₄H₁₁NO₄ calcd. for : C, 65.36 ; H, 4.31 ; N, 5.44%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 855

(lactone CO), 1 700 (CON), 1 610 (C=C) and 1 255 cm⁻¹ (C—O).

(4-Aryl-1-piperazinyl)amides of 2-[4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1H,5H-pyridin-2,6-dion-1-yl]ethanoic acid (14) : A mixture of 11 (38 mmol) and 1-aryl-piperazine (50 mmol) was refluxed in acetone (10 ml) for 2 h. The solvent was then evaporated and the resulting solid was washed with water, treated with aqueous NaHCO₃, and washed with acetone and crystallised from acetone-chloroform mixture (90 : 10, v/v) in 71–92% yield : 14a, m.p. 190–91° ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 718 and 1 665 (imide CO), 1 665 (amide CO), 1 610 (C=C) and 1 245 cm⁻¹ (C—O) ; b, 248–49° ; c, 195–96° δ (CDCl₃) 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.84 (4H, m, Ar-N(CH₂)₂), 3.78 (4H, m, CH₂(CH₂)₂), 3.85 (3H, s, 5-CH₃CO), 3.45 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.86 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 6.66–7.5 (6H, m,

ArH) and 7.66 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, *p*-anisyl); d, 230–31°; e, 223–24°; f, 205–06°.

3-[4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1H, 5H-pyridin-2,6-dion-1-yl]propanoic acid (8): A mixture of 4 (5 g, 25 mmol) and 3-aminopropanoic acid (2.6 g, 30 mmol) was heated at 160–65° for 1 h. The resulting solid was dissolved in aqueous NaHCO₃ and the solution was clarified by animal charcoal, filtered and acidified with HCl. The product was crystallised from H₂O-HOAc (10 : 90, v/v), (4.98 g, 69%), m.p. 194–95°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 950 (OH), 1 730 and 1 680 (CO) and 1 250 cm⁻¹ (C—O).

8-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H,6H-pyrido-[2,1-b](1,3)oxazin-2,6-dione (12): Compound 8 (8 g) was refluxed with Ac₂O (5 ml) and the solution was cooled and filtered. The resulting solid was washed with aqueous NaHCO₃ and water, and crystallised from H₂O-HOAc (10 : 90, v/v), (4.28 g, 93%), m.p. 185–86° (Found: C, 66.32; H, 4.86; N, 5.14. C₁₅H₁₃NO₄ calcd. for: C, 66.41; H, 4.82; N, 5.16%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 800 (lactone CO), 1 670 (pyridone CO), 1 600 (C=C) and 1 250 cm⁻¹ (C—O): δ (CDCl₃) 3.0 (2H, t, J 5 Hz, N-CH₂), 4.43 (2H, t, J 5 Hz, OCH₃), 3.95 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.26 (1H, d, H-9, $J_{o-\tau}$ 2 Hz), 6.63 (1H, H-7, $J_{\tau-\rho}$ 2 Hz), 7.0 (2H, d, J_o 9 Hz, *p*-anisyl) and 7.56 (2H, d, J_o 9 Hz, *p*-anisyl).

(4-Aryl-1-piperazinyl)amides of 3-[4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1H,5H-pyridin-2,6-dion-1-yl]propanoic acid (15): A mixture of 12 (37 mmol) and 1-aryl-piperazine (50 mmol) was refluxed in acetone (10 ml) for 2 h. The solution was then concentra-

ted and cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture (80 : 20, v/v): 5a, m.p. 211–12°; b, 222–23°; c, 200–01°; d, 216–17°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 710 and 1 670 (imide CO), 1 630 (amide CO) and 1 240 cm⁻¹ (C—O); δ (CDCl₃) 2.29 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.7 (2H, t, J_{vis} 9 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.14 (4H, m, Ar-N(CH₂)₂), 3.66 (4H, m, CON(CH₂)₂), 3.8 (2H, s, =C-CH₂CO), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.26 (2H, t, J_{vis} 9 Hz, COCH₂), 6.95, (2H, d, J_o 8 Hz, *p*-tolyl), 7.1 (2H, d, J_o 8 Hz, *p*-tolyl), 6.86 (2H, d, J_o 9 Hz, *p*-anisyl) and 7.54 (2H, d, J_o 9 Hz, *p*-anisyl); e, 209–10°; f, 195–96°; g, 165–66°.

References

1. S. D. SAMANT and R. A. KULKARNI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 819; 1979, **56**, 1002; 1981, **58**, 692; U. V. KORGAONKAR, R. A. KULKARNI and S. D. SAMANT *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 874; B. M. KHADILKAR and S. D. SAMANT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 529.
2. K. STACH and W. POLDINGER, *Prog. Drug Res.*, 1966, **9**, 129; P. A. J. JANSSEN in "Psychopharmacological Agents", ed. M. GORDON, Academic, New York, 1967, Vol. III, p. 199; L. D. WANG and J. N. SOWELL, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1981, **70**, 699; K. SAKAI, N. HEGA and Y. FUJISAWA, *Arch. Int. Pharmacodyn. Ther.*, 1985, **227**, 83; S. KANEKO, Austrian Pat. 334 343/1973 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **87**, 5663); A. PATEL and C. BOURGERY, Ger. Pat. DE 3 306 302/1982 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1984, **100**, 6553); J. KORPAS and G. NOSALOVA, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1978, **30**, 563.
3. S. S. TIWARI and V. K. PANDYE, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1972, **35**, 85.
4. D. B. LIMAYE and V. M. BHAVE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 137.
5. C. B. POLLARD and L. G. MCDOWELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 2199.